

ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION AND ASYMPTOMATIC HYPERURICEMIA: A NEW LOOK AT INTERDEPENDENCE

A.N. Abduvakhitova¹, F.N. Namozov²

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute^{1,2}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14796155>

Abstract. *The objective of this paper is to determine the diagnostic criteria for asymptomatic hyperuricemia as a cardiovascular risk factor, the need for antihypertensive therapy and urate-reducing therapy in patients with hypertension; to develop an algorithm for the management of hypertensive patients with asymptomatic hyperuricemia. The review included 79 sources, including 1 monograph, 11 international and Russian guidelines, consensus documents, 67 reviews, observational, non-randomized, randomized clinical trials, their meta-analyses, requirements for uric acid blood tests. The review presents a definition, prevalence and diagnostic criteria for asymptomatic hyperuricemia, depending on the assessment method and factors affecting the concentration of uric acid, as well as the pathogenetic mechanisms of hyperuricemia. The linear relationship between uric acid level with the risk of hypertension, dyslipidemia, cardiovascular diseases and complications. The review discusses drug-induced hyperuricemia, the effect of various antihypertensive and lipid-lowering drugs on the blood concentration of uric acid, the indications for urate-reducing therapy in asymptomatic hyperuricemia. An algorithm for the management of patients with asymptomatic hyperuricemia and hypertension is proposed.*

Keywords: *asymptomatic hyperuricemia, hypertension, management algorithm.*

Introduction

The association between elevated uric acid (UA) levels and arterial hypertension (AH) has been demonstrated in both animals and humans and is already evident in children and adolescents. The mechanism responsible for elevated blood pressure (BP) in patients with hyperuricemia (HU) is related to both oxidative stress and intracellular urate activity. The increased relative risk (RR) of AH is confirmed by genetic data and several meta-analyses of epidemiological studies. However, there remain ongoing discussions regarding the criteria for determining UA levels in the blood and the frequency of its monitoring depending on cardiovascular risk stratification in AH patients. This includes diagnostic criteria for asymptomatic HU not only in terms of gout risk but also concerning its association with cardiovascular events, drug-induced HU, and the contribution of antihypertensive and lipid-lowering drugs to its development. Additionally, there are debates about indications for urate-lowering therapy in cases of asymptomatic hyperuricemia.

The aim of this descriptive review is to propose a management algorithm for patients with hyperuricemia, including defining diagnostic criteria for asymptomatic HU to assess cardiovascular event risk and adjust antihypertensive and urate-lowering therapy in patients with AH.

Definition of Asymptomatic Hyperuricemia

Asymptomatic HU is defined as elevated UA levels in serum without gouty arthritis, tophi, or urate kidney stones [1, 2]. The serum UA concentration indicative of asymptomatic HU is variable and depends on the method of determination (colorimetric, uricase), dietary factors, adherence to blood sample collection protocols, and diagnostic criteria. Considering body

temperature and urine pH, HU is defined as a serum UA concentration >6.8 mg/dL (405 μ mol/L) at physiological temperature (37.0 °C) and neutral pH levels. From the perspective of gout risk or acute gout recurrence, a normal serum UA level is <6.0 mg/dL (357 μ mol/L) [3, 4]. Some researchers consider serum UA concentrations above 7 mg/dL (416.5 μ mol/L) in men and 6 mg/dL (357 μ mol/L) in women to be associated with gout risk and indicative of HU [5]. At these concentrations, HU may lead to supersaturation and precipitation of monosodium urate crystals. The relationship between HU severity and gout risk was well established in a meta-analysis of 4 observational studies involving 18,889 patients without gout manifestations [6]. The cumulative incidence of clinically evident gout was calculated based on baseline serum UA levels. The incidence of gout (95% confidence interval (CI)) over 15 years was 1.1% (0.9–1.4) at UA levels <6 mg/dL (357 μ mol/L), 16.3% (12.0–20.5) at 8–8.9 mg/dL (476–530 μ mol/L), and 49% (31–67) at levels ≥ 10 mg/dL (595 μ mol/L). These findings indicate that serum UA concentration is a strong, nonlinear predictor of gout. However, only half of patients with asymptomatic HU and serum UA concentrations ≥ 10 mg/dL (595 μ mol/L) developed clinical symptoms of gout within 15 years, suggesting the involvement of other factors in gout pathogenesis [7]. Therefore, the American College of Rheumatology guidelines recommend that gout diagnosis should not be based solely on a single criterion—HU—with a level of evidence of 2aB [8].

Asymptomatic Hyperuricemia and Cardiovascular Risk

Regarding increased risk of mortality, A. Viridis and co-authors (2020) proposed that HU should be considered as serum UA concentrations ≥ 5.1 mg/dL (304 μ mol/L) for women and ≥ 5.6 mg/dL (333 μ mol/L) for men, particularly in patients at high and very high cardiovascular risk. This is associated with a more than twofold increase in cardiovascular mortality risk assessment [9]. Data suggest that for every 1 mg/dL (59.5 μ mol/L) increase in serum UA, the risks of cardiovascular and overall mortality rise by 12% and 20%, respectively [10]. Additionally, a meta-analysis of 32 observational studies in the UK, involving 1,134,073 patients, concluded that the risk of cardiovascular death increases linearly with rising UA levels [11]. Some experts believe that the risk of overall and cardiovascular mortality has a U-shaped relationship with UA concentration. For instance, in a registry of 127,771 patients aged 65 and older with asymptomatic HU, it was found that the risks of overall and cardiovascular mortality increased at UA levels above 8 mg/dL (476 μ mol/L) and below 4 mg/dL (238 μ mol/L) [12]. It is known that UA has several pleiotropic beneficial effects, primarily due to its antioxidant properties [13]. However, a meta-analysis of 17 randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and observational studies showed that asymptomatic HU increases the risk of major cardiovascular events by 72% and all cardiovascular outcomes by 35% [15]. At serum UA levels above 8 mg/dL (477 μ mol/L), the risk of atherosclerotic plaque rupture significantly increases, according to optical coherence tomography data [16]. Asymptomatic HU is an independent risk factor for ventricular arrhythmias and atrial fibrillation in myocardial infarction patients following primary percutaneous coronary intervention [17]. Chronic heart failure (CHF) risk and prognosis are also associated with asymptomatic HU [18]. A meta-analysis of 13 observational studies involving 3,256 patients with asymptomatic HU found that for every 1 mg/dL (59.5 μ mol/L) increase in serum UA, the risk of stroke increases by 10% in men and 11% in women [19].

Prevalence of Gout and Hyperuricemia: HU is a common issue in daily clinical practice, with prevalence estimates ranging from 8.9% to 24.4% in the general population [26]. The prevalence of asymptomatic HU without clinically significant gout is unknown. However, data

from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey suggest that in individuals aged 20 years and older, the prevalence of gout was 3.9%, while HU (UA levels >405 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ or 6.8 mg/dL) was 14.6% [29].

Prevalence of Gout and Hyperuricemia (continued): For the United States, extrapolating these data to the number of affected individuals, the prevalence of gout and asymptomatic HU was estimated at 9.2 million and 32.5 million people, respectively. Notably, over an 8-year period, the number of individuals with these conditions increased by 8.3 and 9.2 million, respectively. It is important to emphasize that gout does not always accompany HU, and HU does not always result in clinical manifestations of gout, including asymptomatic deposition of monosodium urates in synovial fluid.

Risk Factors, Causes, and Pathogenetic Mechanisms of Hyperuricemia: In a large screening study involving more than 2 million participants, the following risk factors for HU development were identified:

Gender: Predominantly male.

Age: HU is less common in men aged 60 years and older.

Body Mass Index (BMI): A BMI $\geq 28 \text{ kg/m}^2$ increases the risk of HU by threefold.

Glomerular Filtration Rate (GFR): A GFR $< 60 \text{ mL/min/1.73 m}^2$ increases the risk of HU by 46%.

Presence of Arterial Hypertension: Increases the risk of HU by 15%.

Presence of Dyslipidemia: Increases the risk of HU by 19%.

Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD): Increases the risk of HU by 55% [30].

Causes and Pathogenetic Mechanisms: The causes and mechanisms of gout and HU development are summarized in Table 1 [31, 32]. To date, 43 genetic defects have been identified that regulate UA concentration and significantly contribute to HU development [33]. For clinical practice, the influence of medications on UA levels is particularly important. Certain drugs are known to elevate UA concentrations (Table 2) [34].

Asymptomatic Hyperuricemia and Cardiovascular Risk Management: The available evidence suggests that asymptomatic HU should be actively monitored and managed, particularly in individuals with high cardiovascular risk. Effective strategies may include dietary modifications, reduction of risk factors such as obesity and dyslipidemia, and careful selection of medications that minimize the risk of exacerbating HU.

Conclusion

Asymptomatic hyperuricemia is a significant clinical condition that extends beyond its association with gout. Its role as an independent risk factor for cardiovascular events, mortality, and metabolic diseases necessitates a more comprehensive approach to its diagnosis, monitoring, and management.

The proposed algorithm for managing patients with HU aims to integrate these insights into clinical practice, emphasizing individualized treatment strategies to mitigate cardiovascular risks while addressing the underlying metabolic imbalances associated with elevated UA levels.

Causes and pathogenetic mechanisms of gout and hyperuricemia development

Mechanisms	Increased purine biosynthesis and/or urate production	Reduced uric acid clearance
Causes		

Mechanisms	Increased purine biosynthesis and/or urate production	Reduced uric acid clearance
Genetic defects		Genetic defects
Clinical conditions	Myelo- and lymphoproliferative disorders, cancer, hemolytic disorders, psoriasis, obesity, tissue hypoxia, glycogen storage diseases (types III, V, VII)	Chronic kidney disease (CKD), gouty nephropathy, heart failure, diabetes mellitus, lactic acidosis, preeclampsia, obesity, hyperparathyroidism, hypothyroidism, sarcoidosis
Drug-, toxin-, and diet-induced hyperuricemia	Alcohol, purine-rich diet, vitamin B12 deficiency, medications	Alcohol, purine-rich diet, vitamin B12 deficiency, medications

Medications increasing uric acid levels with proven or presumed effects

Table 2

Drug Group	With proven effects on uric acid levels	With presumed effects on uric acid levels
Antituberculosis drugs	Acitretin	
Aspirin (low doses)	Didanosine + ritonavir	
Cytotoxic chemotherapy (tyrosine kinase inhibitors, etc.)	Filgrastim	
Diuretics	Alpha-methyldopa	
Immunosuppressants (cyclosporine, tacrolimus)	Omeprazole	
Fructose	Beta-1a interferon + ribavirin	
Lactate infusion	Sildenafil	
Nicotinic acid	Teriparatide	
Testosterone	Ticagrelor	
Xylitol	Topiramate	

Asymptomatic Hyperuricemia and Diuretics: One of the debated questions in managing patients with arterial hypertension (AH) and asymptomatic hyperuricemia (HU)/gout is the use of diuretics. Earlier observational studies indicated that the risk of gout is associated with AH, obesity, and the use of diuretics, predominantly loop diuretics [35, 36]. A dose of 25 mg hydrochlorothiazide increased blood uric acid concentration by 0.8 mg/dL (48 μmol/L). In the large ARIC (Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities) cohort study, the use of any diuretics increased the risk of gout by 48%, thiazide diuretics by 44%, and loop diuretics by 2.31 times over 9 years among 5,789 patients with AH, 37% of whom were on diuretic therapy [37]. However, after adjusting for serum uric acid concentration, the association between diuretic use and gout became null. Nonetheless, serum uric acid levels were 0.72 mg/dL (42.8 μmol/L) higher in individuals taking diuretics compared to those not using them ($p < 0.001$). Combining thiazide diuretics with

angiotensin II receptor antagonists or dihydropyridine calcium channel blockers reduced serum uric acid concentrations compared to monotherapy with diuretics [38]. It is noteworthy that the incidence of gout in patients with asymptomatic HU during thiazide and thiazide-like diuretics therapy for AH is very low. In a large observational study (n = 3,033), the incidence of new gout cases over six years was 1.29% with thiazide diuretics (hydrochlorothiazide, average dose 25 mg) and 1.68% with thiazide-like diuretics (chlorthalidone, average dose 25 mg), with no statistically significant differences between groups (p = 0.27) [39].

Furthermore, an additional analysis of the ALLHAT (Antihypertensive and Lipid-Lowering Treatment to Prevent Heart Attack Trial) RCT, including 23,964 patients with AH, found no significant difference in the odds ratio (OR) of developing gout between those taking lisinopril and those using chlorthalidone: OR 0.85 (95% CI 0.70–1.03, p = 0.100) [40]. There is also evidence that potassium-sparing diuretics may contribute to HU. For example, spironolactone at a dose of 25 mg increased serum uric acid levels in CKD patients over 40 weeks in an RCT [41]. Recent observational studies suggest that the risk of gout associated with diuretics is influenced more by genetic defects in purine metabolism than diuretic use. A UK Biobank study (n = 359,876) evaluated 10 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) associated with HU to assess gout risk in diuretic users [42]. It found that only loop diuretics were associated with gout risk (OR 2.34, 95% CI 2.08–2.63), while thiazide diuretics reduced the risk (OR 0.60, 95% CI 0.55–0.66). The more purine metabolism defects identified, the higher the gout risk, regardless of diuretic use, with additive effects not observed. For patients at high risk of gouty nephropathy, thiazide diuretics may be beneficial in preventing and reducing recurrences of kidney stone formation. A meta-analysis of RCTs showed that thiazide and thiazide-like diuretics prevent kidney stone formation (Table 3) [43].

The impact of thiazide and thiazide-like diuretics on the risk of urolithiasis without consideration of hypercalcemia (randomized clinical trials)

Author, Year	Drug	Dose	Treated/Placebo (N)	Relative Risk of Recurrence	Years of Treatment
Brocks, 1981	Bendroflumethiazide	2.5 mg 3 times daily	33/29	NS	1.6
Scholz, 1982	Hydrochlorothiazide	25 mg twice daily	25/26	NS	1
Mortensen, 1986	Bendroflumethiazide + KCl	2.5 mg 3 times daily	12/10	NS	2
Laerum, 1984	Hydrochlorothiazide	25 mg twice daily	25/25	0.39	3

Author, Year	Drug	Dose	Treated/Placebo (N)	Relative Risk of Recurrence	Years of Treatment
Wilson, 1984	Hydrochlorothiazide	100 mg daily	23/21	0.48	2.8
Robertson, 1985	Bendroflumethiazide	2.5 mg 3 times daily	13/9	0.38	3–5
Ettinger, 1988	Chlorthalidone	25/50 mg once daily	19 (25 mg), 23 (50 mg)/31	0.23	3
Fernandes-Rodrigues, 2006	Hydrochlorothiazide	50 mg daily	50/50	0.56	3

Drugs That Lower Serum Uric Acid Levels

A wide range of therapeutic approaches has been studied to reduce serum uric acid (UA) concentrations in patients with asymptomatic hyperuricemia (AH) and gout, including weight loss, physical activity, coffee, cherries, a low-purine and low-fat diet, lactobacilli, angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs, particularly losartan), calcium channel blockers (especially amlodipine), valsartan/sacubitril, statins, fenofibrate, sevelamer, metformin, sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 (SGLT2) inhibitors, vitamin C, and folic acid [44]. Low-purine diets are a first-line therapy for hyperuricemia and can reduce UA levels by 10–15%.

Effects of Antihypertensive Drugs

Certain antihypertensive drugs, such as losartan and amlodipine, have demonstrated pleiotropic effects in reducing UA levels in patients with gout [45, 46]. However, the uricosuric effect in patients with hypertension (HTN) and AH remains unclear, and its impact on prognosis has not been evaluated.

A recent observational study examined the effect of angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEIs) and ARBs on UA levels in hypertensive patients with AH over seven years. It found that ACEIs did not significantly lower UA levels (5.91 ± 0.03 vs. 5.86 ± 0.03 mg/dL, $p = 0.059$), whereas ARBs exhibited uricosuric effects within three months (5.71 ± 0.01 vs. 5.69 ± 0.01 mg/dL, $p = 0.023$). Significant reductions in UA levels were observed with irbesartan ($n = 1530$, 6.13 ± 0.06 vs. 5.89 ± 0.05 mg/dL, $p < 0.001$) and olmesartan ($n = 2719$, 5.70 ± 0.04 vs. 5.63 ± 0.03 mg/dL, $p = 0.008$) after three months. Both ACEIs and ARBs significantly reduced UA levels in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) with an estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) below 60 mL/min/1.73 m².

Recommendations for Managing AH and HTN

Routine Measurement of UA: UA measurement in serum is recommended as part of routine assessments in patients with HTN and/or cardiovascular risk factors.

UA Thresholds and Repeat Testing: UA concentrations exceeding 360 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ (or 300 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ in patients with two or more cardiovascular risk factors) require repeat testing to confirm AH using consistent methodology and strict pre-analytic conditions.

Specialist Consultation: For confirmed AH, consultation with a rheumatologist is advised to exclude gout, identify underlying causes, and determine management strategies.

Medication Adjustments

Switching from hydrochlorothiazide and loop diuretics to alternative antihypertensives is recommended when possible.

ARBs (preferably losartan) and calcium channel blockers (preferably amlodipine) are recommended for HTN management in patients with AH. Transitioning from other ARBs to losartan is not advised.

It is not recommended to initiate or discontinue low doses of acetylsalicylic acid in patients with hypertension (HTN) and asymptomatic hyperuricemia (AHU) for primary prevention of cardiovascular events [72]. Discontinuation of low doses of acetylsalicylic acid in secondary prevention is also not recommended [68].

In patients with high and very high cardiovascular risk with AHU, it is not recommended to discontinue statins or other lipid-modifying drugs, nor to prescribe fenofibrate [50, 51]. Fibrates should only be used as clinically indicated [73].

Recommendations for strict control of cardiovascular risk factors in all patients with HTN and AHU:

- A target serum uric acid (UA) level of less than 360 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ is recommended for all patients with HTN, while a target of less than 300 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ is recommended for patients with at least two cardiovascular risk factors (HTN, type 2 diabetes, dyslipidemia, target organ damage, or prior cardiovascular diseases) [44, 68].

- To achieve the target UA level, all patients with HTN and AHU are advised to follow a low-purine diet: consumption of red meat, seafood, high-fructose corn syrup, sugar-sweetened soft drinks, and alcohol should be particularly restricted [68].

- For achieving the target UA level, patients with HTN, AHU, and obesity are recommended to lose weight and engage in regular physical activity [74, 75].

- To reduce UA levels, dietary intake of coffee, dairy products, cherries [76, 77], and ascorbic acid [78] is recommended for all patients with HTN and AHU.

Urate-lowering therapy:

Urate-lowering therapy may be prescribed to patients with HTN and AHU through the involvement of an interdisciplinary team, provided there is evidence of greater benefit than the risk of adverse effects for each individual patient [13, 79].

Monitoring UA levels:

It is recommended to monitor serum UA levels in patients with HTN and AHU at least twice a year, or more frequently as indicated [8, 14].

REFERENCES

1. Мазуров В. И. Клиническая ревматология. М.: ГЭОТАР- Медиа; 2021. 696 с. [Mazurov VI. Clinical rheumatology. M.: GEOTAR-Media; 2021. 696 p. In Russian].

2. Dehlin M, Jacobsson L, Roddy E. Global epidemiology of gout: prevalence, incidence, treatment patterns and risk factors. *Nat Rev Rheumatol.* 2020;16(7):380–390. doi:10.1038/s41584-020-0441-1
3. Richette P, Doherty M, Pascual E, Barskova V, Becce F, Castaneda J et al. 2018 updated European League Against Rheumatism evidence-based recommendations for the diagnosis of gout. *Ann Rheum Dis.* 2020;79(1):31–38. doi:10.1136/annrheumdis-2019-215315
4. Richette P, Doherty M, Pascual E, Barskova V, Becce F, Castañeda-Sanabria J et al. 2016 updated EULAR evidence-based recommendations for the management of gout. *Ann Rheum Dis.* 2017;76(1):29–42. doi:10.1136/annrheumdis-2016-209707
5. Hao Y, Li H, Cao Y, Chen Y, Lei M, Zhang T et al. Uricase and horseradish peroxidase hybrid CaHPO nanoflower integrated with transcutaneous patches for treatment of hyperuricemia. *J Biomed Nanotechnol.* 2019;15(5):951–965. doi:10.1166/jbn.2019.2752
6. Dalbeth N, Merriman TR, Stamp LK. Gout. *Lancet.* 2016;388(10055):2039–2052. doi:10.1016/S 0140–6736(16) 00346–9
7. Major TJ, Dalbeth N, Stahl EA, Merriman TR. An update on the genetics of hyperuricaemia and gout. *Nat Rev Rheumatol.* 2018;14(6):341–353. doi:10.1038/s41584-018-0004-x
8. FitzGerald JD, Dalbeth N, Mikuls T, Brignardello-Petersen R, Guyatt G, Abeles AM et al. 2020 American College of Rheumatology Guideline for the management of gout. *Arthritis Care Res (Hoboken).* 2020;72(6):744–760. doi:10.1002/acr.24180. Erratum in: *Arthritis Care Res (Hoboken).* 2020;72(8):1187. Erratum in: *Arthritis Care Res (Hoboken).* 2021;73(3):458.
9. Viridis A, Masi S, Casiglia E, Tikhonoff V, Cicero AFG, Ungar A et al. From the working group on uric acid and cardiovascular risk of the Italian Society of Hypertension. Identification of the uric acid thresholds predicting an increased total and cardiovascular mortality over 20 years. *Hypertension.* 2020;75(2):302–308. doi:10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.119.13643
10. Wang R, Song Y, Yan Y, Ding Z. Elevated serum uric acid and risk of cardiovascular or all-cause mortality in people with suspected or definite coronary artery disease: a meta-analysis. *Atherosclerosis.* 2016;254:193–199. doi:10.1016/j.atherosclerosis.2016.10.006
11. Rahimi-Sakak F, Maroofi M, Rahmani J, Bellissimo N, Hekmatdoost A. Serum uric acid and risk of cardiovascular mortality: a systematic review and dose-response meta-analysis of cohort studies of over a million participants. *BMC Cardiovasc Disord.* 2019;19(1):218. doi:10.1186/s12872-019-1215-z
12. Tseng WC, Chen YT, Ou SM, Shih CJ, Tarng DC; Taiwan Geriatric Kidney Disease (TGKD) Research Group. U-shaped association between serum uric acid levels with cardiovascular and all-cause mortality in the elderly: the role of malnourishment. *J Am Heart Assoc.* 2018;7(4):e007523. doi:10.1161/JAHA.117.007523
13. Brucato A, Cianci F, Carnovale C. Management of hyperuricemia in asymptomatic patients: a critical appraisal. *Eur J Intern Med.* 2020;74:8–17. doi:10.1016/j.ejim.2020.01.001
14. Подагра. Клинические рекомендации [Интернет]. Москва: Ассоциация ревматологов России; 2018. URL: <http://www.ma.cfuv.ru/docs/249620/КР%20Подагра.pdf>. [Gout. Clinical recommendations [Internet]. Moscow: Association of Rheumatologists of Russia; 2018. URL: <http://www.ma.cfuv.ru/docs/249620/КР%20Подагра.pdf>. In Russian].
15. Zhao L, Cao L, Zhao TY, Yang X, Zhu XX, Zou HJ et al. Cardiovascular events in hyperuricemia population and a cardiovascular benefit-risk assessment of urate-lowering

- therapies: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Chin Med J (Engl)*. 2020;133(8):982–993. doi:10.1097/CM9.0000000000000682
16. Kobayashi N, Asai K, Tsurumi M, Shibata Y, Okazaki H, Shirakabe A et al. Impact of accumulated serum uric acid on coronary culprit lesion morphology determined by optical coherence tomography and cardiac outcomes in patients with acute coronary syndrome. *Cardiology*. 2018;141(4):190–198. doi:10.1159/000496053
 17. Hu X, Fu S, Wang S. Hyperuricemia is associated with an increased prevalence of ventricular tachycardia and fibrillation in patients with ST-elevation myocardial infarction after primary percutaneous coronary intervention. *BMC Cardiovasc Disord*. 2022;22(1):199. doi:10.1186/s12872-022-02635-4
 18. Pavlusova M, Jarkovsky J, Benesova K, Vitovec J, Linhart A, Widimsky P et al. Hyperuricemia treatment in acute heart failure patients does not improve their long-term prognosis: a propensity score matched analysis from the AHEAD registry. *Clin Cardiol*. 2019;42(8):720–727. doi:10.1002/clc.23197
 19. Zhong C, Zhong X, Xu T, Xu T, Zhang Y. Sex-specific relationship between serum uric acid and risk of stroke: a dose- response meta-analysis of prospective studies. *J Am Heart Assoc*. 2017;6(4):e005042. doi:10.1161/JAHA.116.005042
 20. Hong C, Zhang Q, Chen Y, Lu Y, Chen L, He Y et al. Elevated uric acid mediates the effect of obesity on hypertension development: a causal mediation analysis in a prospective longitudinal study. *Clin Epidemiol*. 2022;14:463–73. doi:10.2147/ CLEP.S 363429
 21. Wang J, Qin T, Chen J, Li Y, Wang L, Huang H et al. Hyperuricemia and risk of incident hypertension: a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. *PLoS One*. 2014;9(12):e114259. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0114259
 22. Bjornstad P, Laffel L, Lynch J, El Ghormli L, Weinstock RS, Tollefsen SE et al.; TODAY Study Group. Elevated serum uric acid is associated with greater risk for hypertension and diabetic kidney diseases in obese adolescents with type 2 diabetes: an observational analysis from the treatment options for Type 2 Diabetes in Adolescents and Youth (TODAY) Study. *Diabetes Care*. 2019;42(6):1120–1128. doi:10.2337/dc18-2147
 23. Qin T, Zhou X, Wang J, Wu X, Li Y, Wang L et al. Hyperuricemia and the prognosis of hypertensive patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Clin Hypertens (Greenwich)*. 2016;18(12):1268–1278. doi:10.1111/jch.12855
 24. Фомин В. В., Морозова Т. Е., Цурко В. В. Гиперурикемия, подагра и высокий кардиоваскулярный риск — как ими управлять в клинической практике. *Терапевтический архив*. 2019;91(12):75–83. doi:10.26442/00403660.2019.12.000173 [Fomin VV, Morosova TE, Tsurko VV. Hyperuricemia, gout and high cardiovascular risk — how to manage them in clinical practice. *Ther Arch*. 2019;91(12):75–83. doi:10.26442/00403660.2019.12. In Russian].
 25. Куницкая Н. А., Арьев А. Л., Немировский В. С. Роль мочевой кислоты в развитии сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний: от молекулярных механизмов до клинических проявлений. *Врач*. 2022;(6):5–12. doi:10.29296/25877305-2022-06-01 [Kunitskaya NA, Ariev AL, Nemirovsky VS. The role of uric acid in the development of cardiovascular diseases: from molecular mechanisms to clinical manifestations. *Doctor*. 2022;(6):5–12. doi:10.29296/25877305-2022-06-01. In Russian].

26. Skoczyńska M, Chowaniec M, Szymczak A, Langner- Hetmańczuk A, Maciążek-Chyra B, Wiland P. Pathophysiology of hyperuricemia and its clinical significance — a narrative review. *Reumatologia*. 2020;58(5):312–323. doi:10.5114/reum.2020.100140
27. Шальнова С. А., Деев А. Д., Артамонова Г. В., Дупляков Д. В., Ефанов А. Ю., Жернакова Ю. В. и др. Гиперурикемия и ее корреляты в российской популяции (результаты эпидемиологического исследования ЭССЕ-РФ). *Рациональная фармакотерапия в кардиологии*. 2014;10(2):153–159. doi:10.20996/1819-6446-2014-10-2-153-159 [Shalnova SA, Deev AD, Artamonov GV, Duplyakov DV, Efanov AYU, Zhernakova YuV et al. Hyperuricemia and its correlates in the russian population (results of ESSE-RF epidemiological study). *Rat Pharmacother Cardiol*. 2014;10(2):153–159. doi:10.20996/1819-6446-2014-10-2-153-159. In Russian].
28. Елисеев М. С., Новикова А. М. Коморбидность при подагре и гиперурикемии: распространенность, причины, перспективы уратснижающей терапии. *Терапевтический архив*. 2019;91(5):120–128. doi:10.26442/00403660.2019.05.000232 [Eliseev MS, Novikova AM. Comorbidity in gout and hyperuricemia: prevalence, causes, prospects of urate lowering therapy. *Ther Arch*. 2019;91(5):120–128. doi:10.26442/00403660.2019.05.000232. In Russian].
29. Singh G, Lingala B, Mithal A. Gout and hyperuricaemia in the USA: prevalence and trends. *Rheumatology (Oxford)*. 2019;58(12):2177–2180. doi:10.1093/rheumatology/kez196
30. Choi HK, McCormick N, Lu N, Rai SK, Yokose C, Zhang Y. Population impact attributable to modifiable risk factors for hyperuricemia. *Arthritis Rheumatol*. 2020;72(1):157–165. doi:10.1002/art.41067
31. Zhang W, Doherty M, Bardin T, Pascual E, Barskova V, Conaghan P; EULAR Standing Committee for International Clinical Studies Including Therapeutics. EULAR evidence based recommendations for gout. Part II: Management. Report of a task force of the EULAR Standing Committee for International Clinical Studies Including Therapeutics (ESCISIT). *Ann Rheum Dis*. 2006;65(10):131–1324. doi:10.1136/ard.2006.055269
32. Zhu Y, Pandya BJ, Choi HK. Comorbidities of gout and hyperuricemia in the US general population: NHANES 2007–2008. *Am J Med*. 2012;125(7):679–687.e1. doi:10.1016/j.amjmed.2011.09.033
33. Boocock J, Leask M, Okada Y, Matsuo H, Kawamura Y, Shi Y et al.; Asian Genetic Epidemiology Network (AGEN) Consortium. Genomic dissection of 43 serum urate-associated loci provides multiple insights into molecular mechanisms of urate control. *Hum Mol Genet*. 2020;29(6):923–943. doi:10.1093/hmg/ddaa013
34. Ben Salem C, Slim R, Fathallah N, Hmouda H. Drug-induced hyperuricaemia and gout. *Rheumatology (Oxford)*. 2017;56(5):679–688. doi:10.1093/rheumatology/kew293
35. Choi HK, Atkinson K, Karlson EW, Curhan G. Obesity, weight change, hypertension, diuretic use, and risk of gout in men: the health professionals follow-up study. *Arch Intern Med*. 2005;165(7):742–728. doi:10.1001/archinte.165.7.742
36. Hunter DJ, York M, Chaisson CE, Woods R, Niu J, Zhang Y. Recent diuretic use and the risk of recurrent gout attacks: the online case-crossover gout study. *J Rheumatol*. 2006;33(7):1341–1345. Erratum in: *J Rheumatol*. 2006;33(8):1714.
37. McAdams DeMarco MA, Maynard JW, Baer AN, Gelber AC, Young JH, Alonso A et al. Diuretic use, increased serum urate levels, and risk of incident gout in a population-based

- study of adults with hypertension: the atherosclerosis risk in communities cohort study. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2012;64(1):121–129. doi:10.1002/art.33315
38. Bruderer S, Bodmer M, Jick SS, Meier CR. Use of diuretics and risk of incident gout: a population-based case-control study. *Arthritis Rheumatol.* 2014;66(1):185–196. doi:10.1002/art.38203. Erratum in: *Arthritis Rheumatol.* 2014;66(2):427.
39. Wilson L, Nair KV, Saseen JJ. Comparison of new-onset gout in adults prescribed chlorthalidone vs. hydrochlorothiazide for hypertension. *J Clin Hypertens (Greenwich).* 2014;16(12):864–868. doi:10.1111/jch.12413
40. Juraschek SP, Simpson LM, Davis BR, Shmerling RH, Beach JL, Ishak A et al. The effects of antihypertensive class on gout in older adults: secondary analysis of the antihypertensive and lipid-lowering treatment to prevent heart attack trial. *J Hypertens.* 2020;38(5):954–960. doi:10.1097/HJH.0000000000002359
41. Cabrera SE, Edwards NC, Steeds RP, Townend JN, Ferro CJ. Spironolactone increases serum uric acid levels in patients with chronic kidney disease. *J Hum Hypertens.* 2014;28(3):210–211. doi:10.1038/jhh.2013.66
42. Narang RK, Gamble G, Phipps-Green AJ, Topless R, Cadzow M, Stamp LK et al. Do serum urate-associated genetic variants influence gout risk in people taking diuretics? Analysis of the UK Biobank. *J Rheumatol.* 2020;47(11):1704–1711. doi:10.3899/jrheum.191005
43. Cunha TDS, Gomes SA, Heilberg IP. Thiazide and thiazide-like diuretics in nephrolithiasis. *J Bras Nefrol.* 2021;43(1):103–109. doi:10.1590/2175-8239-JBN-2019-0148
44. Petreski T, Ekart R, Hojs R, Bevc S. Hyperuricemia, the heart, and the kidneys — to treat or not to treat? *Ren Fail.* 2020;42(1):978–986. doi:10.1080/0886022X.2020.1822185
45. Eleftheriadis T, Golphinopoulos S, Pissas G, Stefanidis I. Asymptomatic hyperuricemia and chronic kidney disease: Narrative review of a treatment controversial. *J Adv Res.* 2017;8(5):555–560. doi:10.1016/j.jare.2017.05.001
46. Nieradko-Iwanicka B. What is the role of angiotensin receptor blockers in treatment of hyperuricemia coexisting with arterial hypertension? *Reumatologia.* 2018;56(2):106–110. doi:10.5114/reum.2018.75522
47. Kim HS, Kim H, Lee SH, Kim JH. Comparative analysis of the efficacy of angiotensin II receptor blockers for uric acid level change in asymptomatic hyperuricaemia. *J Clin Pharm Ther.* 2020;45(6):1264–1270. doi:10.1111/jcpt.13202
48. Selvaraj S, Claggett BL, Pfeffer MA, Desai AS, Mc Causland FR, McGrath MM et al. Serum uric acid, influence of sacubitril-valsartan, and cardiovascular outcomes in heart failure with preserved ejection fraction: PARAGON-HF. *Eur J Heart Fail.* 2020;22(11):2093–2101. doi:10.1002/ejhf.1984
49. Ogata N, Fujimori S, Oka Y, Kaneko K. Effects of three strong statins (atorvastatin, pitavastatin, and rosuvastatin) on serum uric acid levels in dyslipidemic patients. *Nucleosides Nucleotides Nucleic Acids.* 2010;29(4–6):321–324. doi:10.1080/15257771003741323
50. Zhang J, Ji X, Dong Z, Lu J, Zhao Y, Li R et al. Impact of fenofibrate therapy on serum uric acid concentrations: a review and meta-analysis. *Endocr J.* 2021;68(7):829–837. doi:10.1507/endocrj.EJ20-0808
51. Keller SF, Rai SK, Lu N, Oza A, Jorge AM, Zhang Y et al. Statin use and mortality in gout: a general population-based cohort study. *Semin Arthritis Rheum.* 2018;48(3):449–455. doi:10.1016/j.semarthrit.2018.03.007

52. Jorge AM, Lu N, Keller SF, Rai SK, Zhang Y, Choi HK. The effect of statin use on mortality in systemic autoimmune rheumatic diseases. *J Rheumatol.* 2018;45(12):1689–1695. doi:10.3899/jrheum.171389
53. Zhao Y, Xu L, Tian D, Xia P, Zheng H, Wang L et al. Effects of sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitors on serum uric acid level: a meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Diabetes Obes Metab.* 2018;20(2):458–462. doi:10.1111/dom.13101
54. Unger T, Borghi C, Charchar F, Khan NA, Poulter NR, Prabhakaran D et al. 2020 International Society of Hypertension Global Hypertension Practice Guidelines. *Hypertension.* 2020;75(6):1334–57. doi:10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.120.15026
55. Agarwal V, Hans N, Messerli FH. Effect of allopurinol on blood pressure: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Clin Hypertens.* 2013;15(6):435–442. doi:10.1111/j.1751-7176.2012.00701.x
56. Borghi C, Agnoletti D, Cicero AFG, Lurbe E, Virdis A. Uric acid and hypertension: a review of evidence and future perspectives for the management of cardiovascular risk. *Hypertension.* 2022;79(9):1927–1936. doi:10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.122.17956
57. Tien YY, Shih MC, Tien CP, Huang HK, Tu YK. To treat or not to treat? Effect of urate-lowering therapy on renal function, blood pressure and safety in patients with symptomatic hyperuricemia: a systematic review and network meta-analysis. *J Am Board Fam Med.* 2022;35(1):140–151. doi:10.3122/jabfm.2022.01.210273
58. Goicoechea M, Garcia de Vinuesa S, Verdalles U, Verde E, Macias N, Santos A et al. Allopurinol and progression of CKD and cardiovascular events: long-term follow-up of a randomized clinical trial. *Am J Kid Dis.* 2015;65(4):543–549. doi:10.1053/j.ajkd.2014.11.016
59. Liu P, Chen Y, Wang B, Zhang F, Wang D, Wang Y. Allopurinol treatment improves renal function in patients with type 2 diabetes and asymptomatic hyperuricemia: 3-year randomized parallel-controlled study. *Clin Endocrinol.* 2015;83(4):475–482. doi:10.1111/cen.12673
60. Kimura K, Hosoya T, Uchida S, Inaba M, Makino H, Maruyama S et al. Febuxostat therapy for patients with stage 3 CKD and asymptomatic hyperuricemia: a randomized trial. *Am J Kid Dis.* 2018;72(6):798–810. doi:10.1053/j.ajkd.2018.06.028
61. Sapankaew T, Thadanipon K, Ruenroengbun N, Chaiyakittisophon K, Ingsathit A, Numthavaj P et al. Efficacy and safety of urate-lowering agents in asymptomatic hyperuricemia: systematic review and network meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *BMC Nephrol.* 2022;23(1):223. doi:10.1186/s12882-022-02850-3
62. Чазова И. Е., Жернакова Ю. В., Кисляк О. А., Недогода С. В., Подзолков В. И., Ощепкова Е. В. и др. Консенсус по ведению пациентов с гиперурикемией и высоким сердечно-сосудистым риском. Системные гипертензии. 2019;16(4):8–21. doi:10.26442/2075082X.2019.4.190686 [Chazova IE, Zhernakova YuV, Kislyak OA, Nedogoda SV, Podzolkov VI, Oshchepkova EV et al. Consensus on the management of patients with hyperuricemia and high cardiovascular risk. *Syst Hypertens.* 2019;16(4):8–21. doi:10.26442/2075082X.2019.4.190686. In Russian].
63. Кобалава Ж. Д., Троицкая Е. А. Бессимптомная гиперурикемия: подходы к лечению в аспекте риска развития сердечно-сосудистых и почечных заболеваний. *Кардиология.* 2020;60(12):104–109. doi.org/10.18087/cardio.2020.12.n1158 [Kobalava ZD, Troitskaya EA. Asymptomatic hyperuricemia: treatment approaches according to the risk of

- cardiovascular and renal events. *Kardiologiia = Cardiology*. 2020;60(12):104–109. doi:10.18087/cardio.2020.12.n1158. In Russian].
64. Hakoda M, Kasagi F. Increasing trend of asymptomatic hyperuricemia under treatment with urate-lowering drugs in Japan. *Mod Rheumatol*. 2019;29(5):880–884. doi:10.1080/14397595.2018.1519149
65. Zhang YF, He F, Ding HH, Dai W, Zhang Q, Luan H et al. Effect of uric-acid-lowering therapy on progression of chronic kidney disease: a meta-analysis. *J Huazhong Univ Sci Technolog Med Sci*. 2014;34(4):476–481. doi:10.1007/s11596-014-1302-4
66. Kuwabara M, Niwa K, Hisatome I, Nakagawa T, Roncal- Jimenez CA, Andres-Hernando A et al. Asymptomatic hyperuricemia without comorbidities predicts cardiometabolic diseases: Five-Year Japanese Cohort Study. *Hypertension*. 2017;69(6):1036–1044. doi:10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.116.08998
67. Williams B, Mancia G, Spiering W, Agabiti Rosei E, Azizi M, Burnier M et al. 2018 ESC/ESH Guidelines for the management of arterial hypertension. The Task Force for the management of arterial hypertension of the European Society of Cardiology and the European Society of Hypertension. The Task Force for the management of arterial hypertension of the European Society of Cardiology and the European Society of Hypertension. *J Hypertens*. 2018;36(10):1953–2041. doi:10.1097/HJH.0000000000001940
68. Borghi C, Tykarski A, Widecka K, Filipiak KJ, DomienikKarłowicz J, Kostka-Jeziorny K et al. Expert consensus for the diagnosis and treatment of patient with hyperuricemia and high cardiovascular risk. *Cardiology Journal*. 2018;25(5):545–563. doi:10.5603/CJ.2018.0116
69. [Электронный источник]. URL: <https://yandex.ru/health/turbo/articles?id=7735>
70. [Электронный источник]. URL: <https://www.invitro.ru/library/labdiagnostika/27184>
71. Zhu Y, Pandya BJ, Choi HK. Comorbidities of gout and hyperuricemia in the US general population: NHANES 2007– 2008. *Am J Med*. 2012;125(7):679–687.e1. doi:10.1016/j.amjmed.2011.09.033
72. Gaziano JM, Brotons C, Coppolecchia R, Cricelli C, Darius H, Gorelick PB et al. Use of aspirin to reduce risk of initial vascular events in patients at moderate risk of cardiovascular disease (ARRIVE): a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2018;392(10152):1036–1046. doi:10.1016/S 0140- 6736(18)31924-X
73. Mach F, Baigent C, Catapano AL, Koskinas KC, Casula M, Badimon L et al. 2019 ESC/EAS Guidelines for the management of dyslipidaemias: lipid modification to reduce cardiovascular risk. *Eur Heart J*. 2020;41(1):111–188. doi:10.1093/eurheartj/ehz455. Erratum in: *Eur Heart J*. 2020;41(44):4255. Richette P, Poitou C, Manivet P, Denis J, Bouillot JL, Clément K et al. Weight loss, xanthine oxidase, and serum urate levels: A Prospective Longitudinal Study of obese patients. *Arthritis Care Res (Hoboken)*. 2016;68(7):1036–1042. doi:10.1002/acr.22798
74. Chen JH, Wen CP, Wu SB, Lan JL, Tsai MK, Tai YP et al. Attenuating the mortality risk of high serum uric acid: the role of physical activity underused. *Ann Rheum Dis*. 2015;74(11):2034– 2042. doi:10.1136/annrheumdis-2014-205312
75. Matsumura K, Arima H, Tominaga M, Ohtsubo T, Sasaguri T, Fujii K et al. Effect of losartan on serum uric acid in hypertension treated with a diuretic: the COMFORT study. *Clin Exp Hypertens*. 2015;37(3):192–196. doi:10.3109/10641963.2014.933968

76. Jacob RA, Spinozzi GM, Simon VA, Kelley DS, Prior RL, Hess-Pierce B et al. Consumption of cherries lowers plasma urate in healthy women. *J Nutr.* 2003;133(6):1826–1829. doi:10.1093/ jn/133.6.1826
77. Schlesinger N. Dietary factors and hyperuricaemia. *Curr Pharm Des.* 2005;11(32):4133–4138. doi:10.2174/138161 205774913273
78. Borghi C, Agnoletti D, Cicero AFG, Lurbe E, Virdis A. Uric acid and hypertension: a review of evidence and future perspectives for the management of cardiovascular risk. *Hypertension.* 2022: 101161HYPERTENSIONAHA12217956. doi:10.1161/ HYPERTENSIONAHA.122.17956